

WAGNERISMS IN EUROPE, THE AMERICAS, AND ASIA: THE MANY FORMS OF A UNIFIED GLOBAL PHENOMENON

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Abstract

‘Wagnerism’ was a global musical and cultural phenomenon that, between the second half of the nineteenth century and the early twentieth century, spread across various European, American, and even Asian nations. This phenomenon assumed different characteristics depending on temporal and geographical contexts, leading some scholars to propose the use of the plural form ‘Wagnerisms’ to refer to the culturally specific movements – often framed at the nation-state level – inspired by Wagner’s ideas. A number of scholarly works on Wagnerisms are available in the academic literature, yet a comprehensive study capable of synthesizing Wagner’s reception at global level, considering the main countries, have not yet been identified. This study seeks to address, at least partially, this gap. In particular, through the analysis of existing scholarship, it offers a synthesis of the main features of the most significant Spanish Wagnerisms at global level.

Introduction

The debate surrounding Wagner’s artistic ideas and the cultural movement that embraced his principles, so-called “Wagnerism”, constituted a proto-global cultural phenomenon that emerged during a period of intense nationalism. It was a cultural earthquake with its epicenter in Germany, radiating outward in all directions to reach various European, American, and even Asian nations.

Initially, it was musicians, musicologists, and music critics who engaged in discussion and deepened the understanding of Wagner’s compositions. In time, however, the works of the German master succeeded in captivating audiences around the world. The terms ‘Wagnerian’ or ‘Wagnerite’ came to denote all those who subscribed to Wagner’s ‘-ism’: not only enthusiasts passionate about his music, but also individuals who adopted Wagnerian ideas as a fully fledged ideology. Admirers and detractors of Wagner’s music and thought often found themselves aligned with opposing ‘factions’, each vehemently asserting their stance.

As Jean-Jacques Nattiez has observed, it is useful to distinguish among various forms of Wagnerism, beginning with the fundamental distinction between musical and cultural Wagnerism, and further recognizing the existence of national Wagnerisms that, over time, assumed widely different forms.¹ To borrow a striking expression from Alex Ross, music critic for *The New Yorker* and author of a monumental study on Wagnerism, «each nation saw Wagner through a kind of prism it had fashioned for itself».²

Despite clear divergences in national interpretations, there can be little doubt that Wagner was widely perceived as a German nationalist. This perception stemmed

¹ NATTIEZ 2004, IV, p. 1075.

² ROSS 2022, p. 189.

from the fact that Wagner was one of the most prominent German figures during the Franco-Prussian War and had, almost by default, come to be seen as a representative of the newly unified German Empire. Yet one may question whether this public image corresponded to Wagner's 'true' personality, given that he spent nearly a third of his life outside Germany. In fact, Wagner was never in agreement with German politics, neither before nor after the 1848 March Revolution, nor with the vision of a unified Germany under Prussian hegemony. Indeed, Wagner was far from being pro-Prussian, as is evident from his letters written in 1866, the year of the Austro-Prussian War.³

Nevertheless, Wagner was adopted as a model by nationalist artists at the end of the nineteenth century, a period deeply infused with an ideology in which everything was interpreted in terms of nation, group, and race.⁴

1. European Wagnerisms

1.1 German Confederation

In Germany and the German-speaking regions of Europe, Wagner's librettos and theoretical writings could be read and discussed in their original language, avoiding the mistranslations that, in other parts of Europe, at times led to significant misunderstandings for readers whose native language was not German.⁵

German *Wagnerianertum* was personified by the unsettling figure of Hans von Wolzogen, a philologist and author of the *Thematischer Leitfaden durch die Musik von Richard Wagners Festspiel «Der Ring des Nibelungen»* (1876), as well as the principal editor of the *Bayreuther Blätter*, a journal founded by Wagner and published from 1878 to 1938 (Fig. 1). After the death of the Meister, von Wolzogen became a central figure of the so-called *Wahnfried-Kreis*, a circle that sought to reinterpret Wagner's work through a pseudo-religious lens. Under the direction of

³ This aversion toward the Prussians may be traced back to the period of the Dresden Uprising, during which the Prussian army invaded the Saxon capital. Wagner's active involvement in the revolutionary events of 1849, along with numerous subsequent statements, reveals a clear alignment with the radical left of the political spectrum. Consequently, it is legitimate to question whether Wagner can, in fact, be unambiguously characterized as a German nationalist. v. KUNST 2021, p. 117.

⁴ HOBBSAWM 1990, pp. 101–122.

⁵ For instance, the Italian version of *Lohengrin*, edited by Castrone Salvatore de Marchesi, was rife with unwarranted liberties and contained serious translation errors. In his seminal study on the early Italian adaptations of Wagner's operas, Josef Annen observes: «There is no doubt that Wagner's admiration for the first performances of his *Lohengrin* in Bologna would have been far less enthusiastic and sincere had he known that the text sung by the Italian performers was nothing more than a crude distortion of his libretto» («Non c'è dubbio che l'ammirazione del Wagner per le prime rappresentazioni del suo *Lohengrin* a Bologna sarebbe stata meno grande e sincera se egli avesse saputo che il testo cantato dagli artisti italiani non era altro che una brutta contraffazione del suo libretto»). ANNEN 1943, p. 33. The language barrier in the Scandinavian and Baltic countries of Northern Europe was not as impenetrable as one might assume, since German was – and continues to be – widely spoken in these regions, dating back to the era of the Hanseatic League. When the first volumes of Wagner's *Gesammelte Schriften und Dichtungen* were published in the 1870s, they were read in Northern Europe with the same immediacy and interest as in Germany itself. SALMI 2005, p. 148.

Cosima Wagner, the journal eventually transformed into a platform for racist ideology.⁶ Later, in December 1928, von Wolzogen was one of the signatories of the founding manifesto of the *Kampfbund für deutsche Kultur*.⁷

During the Nazi period, in March 1936, von Wolzogen published an article in the *Zeitschrift für Musik* in which he praised Hitler as «the incarnation of the *völkisch* spirit» and compared him to Wagner.⁸ This dark branch of Wagner reception in Germany, centered around the Wagner family itself, was also represented by other ambiguous figures, such as the racists Ludwig Schemann and Houston Stewart Chamberlain (Wagner's son-in-law), whose writings, influenced by Gobineau, exalted the concept of the 'Aryan race'. Although this strain of *Wagnerianertum* initially constituted a radical fringe, it undeniably exerted some influence over both the German and international reception of Wagner.

Musically, numerous composers in the German-speaking world adopted Wagner's model of music drama and his musical innovations. Their works, however, cannot be reduced to a single stylistic denominator. Among the most important composers influenced by Wagner were Anton Bruckner, Gustav Mahler, Hugo Wolf, Engelbert Humperdinck, Felix Draeseke, Richard Strauss, Hans Pfitzner, Franz Schreker, as well as the *avant-garde* composers of the Second Viennese School: Arnold Schoenberg, Alban Berg, and Anton Webern.

1.2 The Austro-Hungarian Empire

In the final decades of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy, the various ethnic groups within this multinational empire began to pay increasing attention to questions of national identity. It is notable that each of these groups appropriated Wagner's music in support of often opposing nationalist agendas.

For instance, among the German-speaking population of the empire, performances of works such as *Lohengrin* became symbolic of presumed Germanic cultural superiority. However, this did not prevent Hungarians, Slovaks, and other non-German-speaking groups from employing Wagner's music and librettos for their own nationalist purposes.

The Slovak composer Ján Levoslav Bella (1843–1936), a respected musician and Catholic priest who later converted to Protestantism, chose Wagner's unfinished libretto *Wieland der Schmied* as the basis for a Slovak national opera.⁹ The libretto, thematically close to *Siegfried* and reminiscent of other Wagnerian dramatic projects left incomplete, such as *Achill* and *Friedrich I*, conceived around the 1848–49 Dresden Revolution in which Wagner actively participated, became a medium for national expression. Bella was not the only composer to set *Wieland* to music. The

⁶ KUNST 2021, p. 92.

⁷ KLEE 2007, p. 675.

⁸ *Ibidem*.

⁹ LENGOVÁ 2013, pp. 446–447.

Hungarian Ödön von Mihalovich (1842–1929), an important organizer of Hungarian musical life and a prolific composer (though largely forgotten today), did the same.

In Bohemia, two of the most prominent Czech national composers, Antonín Dvořák and Bedřich Smetana, also demonstrated strong Wagnerian sympathies. Dvořák experienced two Wagnerian phases in his long career, at its beginning and again toward the end. Smetana, for his part, not only followed the new German model of composition but was also well-versed in Wagner's aesthetics.¹⁰ He had planned to establish a school of opera that would provide not only musical training but also instruction in the dramatic arts, an idea inspired by Wagner's writings on theatre reform, such as the *Bericht an Seine Majestät Ludwig II von Bayern über eine in München zu errichtende deutsche Musikschule* (1865).

1.3 France

The history of Wagner's reception in France began with the ill-fated Paris premiere of *Tannhäuser* in 1861, an event orchestrated by Countess Pauline von Metternich, who had lobbied for the first complete staging of a Wagner opera in France, with the support of Napoleon III. Despite the Parisian debacle, Wagner came to be viewed in France as a symbol of modernity, and *wagnérisme* found its prophet in Charles Baudelaire. The *Revue wagnérienne*, founded in 1885 by Édouard Dujardin, published for three years contributions from fervent Wagnerians, including Verlaine and Mallarmé, and played a vital role in promoting Symbolism in literature.¹¹ Wagnerian subjects, especially those drawn from *Tannhäuser*, also inspired painters such as Cézanne, while Renoir managed to paint a portrait of Wagner in Palermo in 1882, with the composer sitting for the occasion (Fig. 2).

It is also worth noting that it was a French writer, Judith Gautier (daughter of Théophile Gautier and, for a time, the wife of Catulle Mendès), who encouraged Wagner to delve into Eastern thought and culture, contributing to the genesis of *Parsifal*.¹²

Among the many French composers influenced by Wagner's aesthetics were César Franck, Emmanuel Chabrier, Camille Saint-Saëns, Ernest Chausson, and

¹⁰ KUNST 2021, p. 102.

¹¹ *Ivi*, p. 142. In his journal *Revue wagnérienne*, Édouard Dujardin also championed free verse and the technique of *interior monologue*. Just as Wagner's music unfolded through a sequence of motifs evoking emotional states, the interior monologue was defined as «a succession of short phrases, each of which expresses, in turn, a movement of the soul; and the resemblance lies in the fact that they are not linked by a rational order, but by a purely emotional one, entirely outside of any intellectual or logical organization».

¹² The daughter of the writer Théophile Gautier, she studied Chinese language and literature, and published translations of Chinese poetry collections as well as novels with exotic themes. Following her separation from her husband, Catulle Mendès, she settled in an apartment in Paris decorated in Oriental style, where she hosted guests every Sunday while devoting herself to the study of occultism and Celtic legends. She was a friend of Wagner, with whom she maintained an extensive correspondence that still survives. Judith Gautier also authored a memoir entitled *Visite à Richard Wagner*.

above all Vincent d'Indy.¹³ Around the turn of the twentieth century, several operas in Wagnerian style were composed in France, including *Le roi Arthus* by Chausson (1855–1899), *Gwendoline* and *Briseïs* by Chabrier (1841–1894), *Hulda* by Franck (1822–1890), *Ariane et Barbe-Bleue* by Paul Dukas (1865–1935), and *Pénélope* by Gabriel Fauré (1845–1924).

However, Wagner's reputation in France suffered a severe blow after the defeat at Sedan. His publication of the satirical play *Eine Kapitulation. Lustspiel in antiker Manier* (1870), mocking the besieged Parisians, deeply offended even the most passionate *wagneristes*. Apart from *Lohengrin*, performed in Nice in 1881, no full Wagner opera was staged in Paris after the Franco-Prussian War until 1887, when *Lohengrin* was performed amidst nationalistic protest. A further scandal erupted during a subsequent staging in 1891. Nonetheless, between 1900 and 1914, Wagner's music dramas gradually regained favor with the French public.

1.4 United Kingdom

In the United Kingdom, Wagnerism was a relatively unpolarised phenomenon, far removed from the impassioned debates that characterised its reception in France. It gained momentum in the 1870s, although its roots can be traced back to the 1850s, when it first emerged as an elite cultural trend. During that decade, George Eliot, who was the first writer to use the term *Wagnerism* in her essay *Liszt, Wagner and Weimar*, sought in her monumental narrative works the same 'organic unity' she admired in the German composer's music. Meanwhile, Queen Victoria and the Prince of Wales officially incorporated the third-act chorus from *Lohengrin* into the royal wedding protocol.¹⁴

In 1870, Wagner's *Der fliegende Holländer* was staged in London as the first complete opera by the composer to be performed in Britain. Two years later, the London branch of the Wagner Society was founded, and the German composer rapidly came to be seen by English artists as a herald of the Arthurian cycle, influencing major Pre-Raphaelite painters such as Edward Burne-Jones, whose *Laus Veneris* (Fig. 3) drew inspiration from *Tannhäuser*.¹⁵ Neologisms such as *Wagnerolatry* and *Wagneridolatry* were coined to describe the often mystical

¹³ ROSS 2003, pp. 209–213. Vincent d'Indy (1851–1931), a composition teacher at the Schola Cantorum in Paris, was a central figure in the history of French music and, in his time, the most influential among the French 'adepts' of Wagner. *Parsifal* served as a direct source of inspiration for d'Indy's opera *Fervaal*, which was based on the poem *Axel* by the Swedish writer Esaias Tegnér. While the original setting of the narrative was in Scandinavia, d'Indy – who, like Wagner, also wrote his own libretti – relocated the story to the south of France in the eighth century. A fervent nationalist and antisemite, d'Indy went so far as to publish tables of leitmotive corresponding to his opera.

¹⁴ George Eliot, the pseudonym of Mary Anne (Marian) Evans, traveled to Weimar in 1854 to attend performances of *Tannhäuser*, *Der fliegende Holländer*, and *Lohengrin*, and engaged in extended discussions with Liszt about Wagner. The terms *wagnerism* and *wagnerianism*, largely synonymous and coined by Eliot herself, are used to denote both the distinctive artistic principles associated with Wagner and the powerful fascination his music exerted upon his admirers.

¹⁵ The experience of listening to *Tannhäuser* and reading an essay by Baudelaire inspired Swinburne to compose the verses *Laus Veneris*, and inspired painters Burne-Jones and Morris to create works that were considered scandalous at the time. ROSS 2022, pp. 172-173.

eneration of Wagner and his work, frequently satirised in *Punch*, Britain's leading humour and caricature magazine.¹⁶ Wagner's triumphant reception at the 1877 London Wagner Festival, attended by the Prince of Wales, reflected the enthusiasm of a diverse audience. Performed in Italian, his operas enjoyed such success that even children's literature was swept up in the cultural wave: following the first London staging of the *Ring* cycle in 1882, numerous adapted editions of Wagner's work were published for younger readers, suitably purged of controversial scenes and themes such as incest.

A few years later, *The Meister*, a journal founded in 1888 by physician William Ashton Ellis, began publishing English translations of Wagner's prose works, interpreting them through a theosophical lens. At the same time, George Bernard Shaw famously offered a socialist reading of the *Ring* cycle in his essay *The Perfect Wagnerite*.¹⁷

Figures such as Annie Horniman, founder of Dublin's Abbey Theatre, and W. B. Yeats went so far as to envision transforming the nascent theatre into a sister institution to Bayreuth, adopting it as a symbol of Irish national pride, in line with the ethos of the Irish Cultural Revival. Wagnerian composers such as Charles Villiers Stanford (1852–1924) and Arnold Bax (1883–1953) emerged within this context.¹⁸

¹⁶ Numerous English neologisms derived from Wagner's name, many of which originated between the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, continue to be in use today. Among the more frequently encountered is the term *wagneresque*, employed both as an adjective, to describe the style of a musical composition that exhibits Wagnerian characteristics, and as a noun, referring to a piece written as a tribute to Wagner. Adverbs such as *wagnerianly* («in the manner of Wagner») are also attested, though care should be taken not to confuse it with *wagnerially*, which may be more accurately paraphrased as «in a way that vaguely evokes Wagner». Other expressions, oscillating between the serious and the facetious, refer to various forms of 'pathology', including a specific type of neurosis termed *wagnerosis*. This affliction, said to have affected, among others, the Irish composer Charles Villiers Stanford, is characterized by an obsessive preoccupation with the systematic use of leitmotive, as found in Wagner's works. Among these pathologies, *wagneritis* also deserves mention. According to the *Oxford English Dictionary*, the word seems to appear for the first time in the writings of George Bernard Shaw in 1889. The Irish Nobel laureate used it to denote a 'disease' that seemed to afflict a certain number of admirers of the German composer's works, and he described it as follows: «a disease not uncommon among persons who have discovered the merits of Wagner's music by reading about it, and among those disciples who know no other music than his». (SHAW 1898, p. 55). The *Wagneritis* appears to partially coincide, at least according to the *Urban Dictionary*, the largest online vocabulary of neologisms and slang in the English language, with the well-known depressive syndrome that affects *hikikomori*: «Wag-ner-i-tis : noun : an acute contagious disease that directly effects the ability to go to a job or school. Symptoms vary from a simple inability to arrive on time to severe symptoms which include unwillingness to get out of bed and/or refusal to be employed. Often times the disease is passed easily among close friends, family and co-workers. If not addressed early on, Wagneritis can lead to being broke, living with parents, and/or Ergophobia» (Entry from the online slang dictionary of the English language, <https://www.urbandictionary.com/define.php?term=Wagneritis>, accessed: 25/07/2025). Finally, one may also encounter terms used to designate a person afflicted by a pronounced obsession, regardless of whether it pertains specifically to Wagner's *Ring* cycle, the context in which the words were originally coined. *Ringnut* and *Ringhead* are such examples, both of which may be rendered by the term *fanatic*.

¹⁷ SHAW 1898.

¹⁸ REGGIANI 2015, p. 207. The Irish composer Stanford served as organist at Trinity College, Cambridge, and was one of the founders of the Royal College of Music; the English composer Bax, captivated by Celtic culture, moved to Dublin and composed a symphonic poem for large orchestra, *Tintagel*, which incorporates themes from *Tristan*.

1.5 Italy

A key moment in the Italian reception of Wagner was the successful performance of *Lohengrin* in Bologna in 1871, conducted by Angelo Mariani with Italo Campanini singing the title role. Though Wagner was unable to attend, the city of Bologna awarded him honorary citizenship. Italian intellectuals were strongly drawn to the composer, beginning with Arrigo Boito. Later composers such as Giacomo Puccini, Franco Alfano, Umberto Giordano, and Ermanno Wolf-Ferrari would also come under Wagner's influence.¹⁹ Ottorino Respighi, too, whose father, a fervent Wagnerian, had his copy of *Die Walküre* brought to him on his deathbed, could not escape the powerful sway of the German master.²⁰

In literature, Giosuè Carducci was fascinated by the mythology of the *Nibelungen*, which he sought to blend with Greek myth, as in his poem *Alle Valchirie* (1898), written for Queen Elisabeth's funeral and portraying the Valkyries escorting the deceased monarch to the cradle of civilisation, Greece. Carducci's *Presso l'urna di Percy Byshe Shelley* also reflects this syncretic approach.

However, it was above all Gabriele D'Annunzio who fully embraced Wagnerism after attending a performance of *Tristan und Isolde* in 1892. His admiration for the 'Gesù di Bayreuth', as he called Wagner, is evident in his novel *Il trionfo della morte* (1894), steeped in the emotional atmosphere of *Tristan*, and marked by a narrative technique that echoes Wagner's use of *leitmotive*: repeated phrases and mirrored openings and closings of paragraphs.²¹

In *Il fuoco* (1900), Wagner appears as a character, and the novel's final image captures his funeral. The protagonist, Stelio Effrena, a young poet, carries the composer's coffin with his friends, as "il mondo intero pare diminuito di valore" upon Wagner's death.²²

Arturo Graf (1848–1913) also responded to Wagnerian themes: following the first Italian performance of *Der fliegende Holländer*, he composed the poem *Il vascello fantasma*, which appeared in his major poetic collection *Medusa* (1880). His poem *Lo gnomo* revisits themes from the *Ring* cycle, though in parodic fashion: the gnome resigns himself to «davvero e per sempre un mito» dopo essere stato «poco men che stroncato da un'indecente automobile».²³ In his novel *Senilità*, Italo Svevo included a passage set during a performance of *Die Walküre* in Trieste, and in a separate article reviewing Wagner's autobiography, he remarked that «Wagner è condotto da un Dio, l'arte, a traverso ad un mondo di essere inferiori e nemici».²⁴

¹⁹ STREICHER 1999.

²⁰ STREICHER 1999, p. 7.

²¹ CRESTI 2012, p. 129.

²² D'ANNUNZIO 1995, p. 297. «the world itself seemed to diminish in value».

²³ GRAF 1906, p. 98. «becoming forevermore a myth» after being «nearly flattened by a vulgar automobile».

²⁴ Italo Svevo (pseud. E. Samigli), *Indipendente*, Trieste, 22 december 1884. «Wagner is led by a God, the Art, through a world of inferior and hostile beings».

Italian Wagnerism also found expression in the visual arts, most notably in the work of Mariano Fortuny y Madrazo, a Spanish-born artist who adopted Italy as his home and settled in Venice. His paintings are imbued with Wagnerian themes, as seen in *L'abbraccio di Siegmund and Sieglinde* (1893), *Wotan colpisce la roccia con la lancia* (1895), and *Le fanciulle-fiore* (1896), Fig. 4.

Fortuny also worked in sculpture and theatrical design, creating sets and costumes for the 1900 *Tristan und Isolde* premiere at La Scala. Inspired by Wagner and Bayreuth, he experimented with stage lighting, ultimately inventing the 'cupola Fortuny' ('Fortuny dome'), an innovative system that diffused light to replace traditional direct lighting. The dome was installed in La Scala and all major German theatres.²⁵

1.6 Iberian Peninsula

Unlike in France, where Wagner's initial reception was shaped by political and aristocratic support, Wagnerism in the Iberian Peninsula developed without significant intervention from the nobility. Theoretical writings and musical dramas by Wagner began to circulate publicly in Spain and Portugal in the 1860s, following the Paris premiere of *Tannhäuser*. Yet nearly two decades passed before any of his operas were staged. The Wagner Society in Madrid was founded only in 1911, forty years later than the Barcelona Wagner Society (one of the members of the Madrid Wagner Society was Rogelio de Egusquiza, a friend of Wagner and a famous painter of wagnerian subjects, Fig. 5).

Two key obstacles hindered the development of Spanish and Portuguese Wagnerism at national level. First, the musical infrastructure in both countries lagged behind other European nations. There were few opera houses capable of staging the Romantic repertoire, limited orchestral activity, and few symphonic seasons. Madrid's Sociedad de Conciertos was founded only in 1866, and Lisbon's *Concertos Populares* were not inaugurated until the late 1870s.²⁶

Second, in Spain at least, Wagnerian reception was marked by significant regional fragmentation. The aristocratic public in Madrid largely ignored Wagner's works.²⁷ In Catalonia, the Basque Country, and Galicia, his operas were reinterpreted through nationalist or regionalist lenses. These regions saw the rise of a new bourgeois class

²⁵ The *Cupola* was a complex lighting system that liberated theatrical scenography from the constraints of traditional staging through the use of indirect and diffused light. The Parisian theatre scene showed particular interest in this innovation, but it was under the patronage of the Countess of Béarn that Fortuny's technical revolution found its fullest expression. Between 1903 and 1906, the Countess's private theatre was equipped with an integrated and updated system comprising the *Cupola*, indirect lighting, and the projection of colored skies and clouds. Fortuny's system was later manufactured by AEG and implemented in major German theatres. The *Cupola* was installed at the Teatro alla Scala in Milan in 1900. LA SCENA DI MARIANO FORTUNY, <http://www.arabeschi.it/la-scena-mariano-fortuny/> (accessed: 25/07/2025).

²⁶ SUÁREZ GARCÍA 2005, p. 73; SANTOS 2009, 142.

²⁷ BORRELL 1912.

with aspirations for autonomy or even secession and wagnerism was highly connected with this phenomenon.²⁸

In Catalonia, there were plans to build a theatre specifically dedicated to staging Wagner's works. Had it materialised, this venue would have been the first purpose-built theatre for *Parsifal* outside of Bayreuth after the exclusive performance rights expired.²⁹ Similarly, the Basque Country witnessed the emergence of a regional Wagnerism, whose chief representatives were composers such as Usandizaga and Guridi.³⁰ In Galicia, Wagnerian influence surfaced in the early twentieth century, leading to proposals for an opera that would merge Germanic and Galician elements.³¹

1.7 Northern Europe

In Northern Europe, *Rienzi* was performed in Sweden as early as 1865, following initial discussions about Wagner that had begun in Stockholm periodicals and journals during the 1850s. Swedish composers and librettists proudly claimed to be Wagner's true heirs, pointing to his use of Norse mythology from the *Edda* in his music dramas.³² Among them, Andreas Hallén, Wilhelm Peterson-Berger, and Wilhelm Stenhammar, who composed *Tirfing*, wrote operas they conceived as direct continuations of Wagner's artistic project. This genre was later pejoratively labelled "Viking opera," due to its perceived lack of originality.

In Finland, a nation that had been part of the Swedish Kingdom until 1809 and would only gain independence from the Russian Empire in 1917, Wagner's music was received significantly later than in Sweden. The Finnish premiere of *Tannhäuser* took place in Helsinki only in 1904. Finnish composers, like their Swedish counterparts, were particularly captivated by *Parsifal* and other late works written after *Siegfried*, and some composed operas directly influenced by Wagner. In both Sweden and Finland – as in other European national contexts – the prevailing strategy for assimilating Wagner's music was to integrate folk melodies or elements of vernacular music into orchestral scores, as evidenced in Peterson-Berger's operas or those of Finnish composer Erkki Melartin (Fig. 6). Often dubbed 'the Finnish Wagner', Melartin incorporated the *kantele* in his opera *Aino* (1912).³³

According to Martin Kunst's research, during the first half of the twentieth century, Wagner's popularity in Sweden significantly outpaced that in Finland. The influence of Wagner's dense motivic development and quasi-polyphonic textures,

²⁸ GALBIATI 2025.

²⁹ JANÉS I NADAL 1983.

³⁰ ODRIÓZOLA OTAMENDI 2022.

³¹ GALBIATI 2025.

³² KUNST 2021, p. 116.

³³ Similarly, in France, d'Indy composed the *Symphonie sur un chant montagnard français* in 1886, in which the folkloric element is embedded within a highly elaborate orchestration and harmonic complexities that clearly reveal Wagnerian influence. SALVETTI, 1991, p. 38.

particularly characteristic of his middle and late style, is more readily discernible in Swedish orchestral compositions of the period than in their Finnish counterparts.³⁴ Furthermore, Wagnerism in Sweden during this time displayed closer affinities with German *Wagnerianertum*, including right-wing political tendencies and antisemitism among some of its supporters, features that were notably absent from Finnish Wagnerism.³⁵

1.8 Russia and the Soviet Union

The reception of Wagner in Russia, and later in the Soviet Union, was marked by fluctuating fortunes. This complex trajectory has been thoroughly examined by Rosamund Bartlett in her seminal monograph on Russian Wagnerism, which highlights the composer's influence on Russian writers, musicians, and artists of the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, including Symbolist authors Vyacheslav Ivanov, Andrey Bely, Emil Medtner, Lev Koblyinski-Ellis, and Aleksandr Blok.³⁶ Painters such as Mikhail Vrubel also admired Wagner and found inspiration in his works. Wagner's name appears to have been known among Russian intellectuals as early as 1841.³⁷ However, the decisive breakthrough occurred in the following decade, when Wagner's Zurich-period writings were first published in Russian translation and, on March 15, 1856, the overture to *Tannhäuser* was performed at a concert of the St. Petersburg Philharmonic Society. The most fervent advocate of Wagner in Russia during the 1850s and 1860s was Alexander Serov (1820–1871), a composer and music critic (Fig. 7). Following a visit to Germany in 1858, during which he heard *Tannhäuser* six times in six days, Serov, in a state of near-mystical fervour, declared himself the «apostle of Wagner in Russia» and devoted considerable effort to disseminating the music and writings of his 'divinity'.³⁸

When Wagner visited St. Petersburg and Moscow in 1863, his music had not yet acquired the political overtones it would later assume, particularly in relation to Baltic provinces' demands for autonomy from the Russian Empire. Nevertheless, Wagner was discreetly monitored by the authorities during his visit, particularly during his meetings with Francophile members of the nobility.

The Russian premiere of the *Ring* cycle in 1889 met with extraordinary acclaim and ignited over a decade of intense enthusiasm among Russian theatre-goers at the turn of the century. Even those composers who initially opposed Wagner, such as Nikolai Rimsky-Korsakov (1844–1908) and Alexander Borodin (1833–1887) of *The*

³⁴ KUNST 2021, p. 116.

³⁵ *Ibidem*.

³⁶ BARTLETT 1995.

³⁷ SALMI 2005, p. 107.

³⁸ BARTLETT 1995, pp. 82-89. In a letter to his friends written in 1858, he declared: «I am fascinated by Wagner. I play and study his works, read about him, speak about him, write about him, preach about him. I am proud to be his apostle in Russia». The following year, Serov returned to Germany and attended a performance of *Lohengrin* in Weimar. He was later able to meet the composer in Switzerland.

The Group of five, eventually acknowledged the value of his music, as did Pyotr Ilyich Tchaikovsky (1840–1893).

By the end of the nineteenth century, Wagner's entire operatic oeuvre had been staged in St. Petersburg, and leading directors and theatrical innovators such as Sergei Diaghilev (1872–1929), Vsevolod Meyerhold (1874–1940), and Sergei Eisenstein (1898–1948) turned their attention to his work.

According to Bartlett, a distinctly Russian form of Wagnerism emerged during this period, known as *Wagnerovshchina*.³⁹ This variant interpreted Wagner's operas as a source of mystical and religious spirituality, a dimension that, in the view of its Russian adherents, only Russians were destined to fully explore.⁴⁰

At the outbreak of World War I, Tsar Nicholas II banned the performance of Wagner's music. This prohibition, however, was lifted in 1917 by Lenin, a devoted admirer of Wagner, thus allowing Wagnerian theories to play a prominent role in shaping the cultural ambitions of the early Soviet state.⁴¹

In the early years of the USSR, Wagner's music dramas were treated as experimental laboratories for futuristic and avant-garde stage productions, reflecting the optimism of the post-revolutionary era. During this period, Wagner was interpreted as a revolutionary socialist.⁴²

By the late 1920s, however, Wagner's later writings, imbued with Schopenhauerian pessimism and mysticism, were condemned by Soviet censors as reactionary and incompatible with the principles of Communism and the cultural revolution.⁴³ Performances of Wagner's operas sharply declined, and the Wagner Societies that had emerged in various Soviet cities were dissolved by the Communist Party in 1930.

A decade later, to commemorate the Molotov–Ribbentrop Pact, Eisenstein was commissioned to stage *Die Walküre*. Although he did not endorse German policy, the Soviet director depicted a symbolic union between the two states, interpreting Wagnerian philosophy as emblematic of Germany and aligning it with Soviet communism.

With the outbreak of World War II, Wagner's music was once again banned in the Soviet Union, as he came to be identified with Nazi Germany. This marked the definitive end of the *Wagnerovshchina*. Wagner's music would only be rehabilitated in the USSR during the period of *glasnost* at the end of the 1980s.

³⁹ BARTLETT 1995, p.103.

⁴⁰ *ivi*, p.111.

⁴¹ FAIRCLOUGH 2012, p. 2.

⁴² BARTLETT 1995, pp. 221–259.

⁴³ *Ibidem*.

2. The Americas

2.1 United States

Wagnerism also spread to the United States, where Yankee audiences recognized in Wagnerian heroes the same values of strength and heroism with which they identified themselves. At the same time, as occurred elsewhere in the world, the works of the German composer were regarded as expressions of German nationalism, especially by German immigrants in the United States.⁴⁴

A true cult of the Master flourished: numerous streets in major cities were named after characters from Wagner's operas, and to this day it is still possible to glide across the serene waters of a pond in Boston's centrally located Public Garden aboard swan-shaped boats, the *Swan Boats*, designed in 1877 by boat builder Robert Paget, who was inspired by *Lohengrin* (Fig. 8).⁴⁵

Also in Boston, the American art collector and patron Isabella Stewart Gardner, founder of the museum that bears her name, was known for her pilgrimages to Bayreuth. The Gardner Museum still houses various Wagnerian relics, including a first-edition *Parsifal* libretto, set design sketches for *Die Meistersinger*, an autograph letter from the composer, and an ivy leaf taken from his grave.

Several statues of Wagner were also erected in the United States, many of which have, at least so far, withstood the recent iconoclastic zeal of the "woke" movement, which has called for their removal. Remarkably, the first Wagner opera performed in the United States, *Tannhäuser*, at the Metropolitan Opera in New York in 1859, predated its premieres in both Paris and London.

Early twentieth-century Wagnerian productions at the Metropolitan Opera were notable for their splendor. In 1903, the *Parsifal* was performed in its entirety at the Met, despite legal action from Cosima Wagner. This defied Bayreuth's exclusive performance rights, made possible by the fact that the United States had not signed the Berne Convention (1886), and therefore the opera was not protected under German copyright law.

Wagnerism also influenced architecture: in 1886, Sullivan and Adler designed and constructed in Chicago a grand auditorium intended to rival the Metropolitan Opera, modeled explicitly after the amphitheater layout of Bayreuth (Fig. 9).

This design enabled audiences to experience the musical artwork without seating privileges based on social class.⁴⁶

⁴⁴ KUNST 2021, p. 97.

⁴⁵ For the history of these boats see the website: <https://swanboats.com/>, rich in iconographic material.

⁴⁶ In the same years, in New York, Cram and Goodhue designed and built the Church of St. Bartholomew, inspired by the atmosphere of the final act of *Parsifal*. The carillon of Riverside Church in the same city still marks each quarter hour with a sequence of notes based on the *Parsifal* bell motif. Walt Whitman, too, was deeply fascinated by Wagner, and his name was frequently associated with that of the German composer by contemporary critics. Whitman was even referred to as the 'Wagner of poets' for having abandoned regular meter, just as Wagner had rejected traditional cadences.

Toward the end of the nineteenth century, plans were even discussed to build a theater in New York exclusively dedicated to a Wagnerian festival, a replica of Bayreuth, but the project was never realized.⁴⁷

One particularly compelling aspect of Wagner's reception in the New World was the debate over whether his art could be considered democratic. In the United States, the prevailing image was that of the mature Wagner, the composer who sought aristocratic patrons to support Bayreuth and who, in 1876, composed the *Großer Festmarsch zur Eröffnung der hundertjährigen Gedenkfeier der Unabhängigkeitserklärung der Vereinigten Staaten von Amerika* («Grand Festival March for the Opening of the Centennial Celebration of the Declaration of Independence of the United States of America»).

This rather mediocre composition, written for the astronomical sum of \$5,000 (roughly equivalent to \$100,000 today), sat uneasily alongside the image of the young democratic revolutionary who had participated in the Dresden Uprising of 1848–49.⁴⁸

2.2 Latin America

In South America, particularly in Brazil, Argentina, Cuba, and Mexico, *Lohengrin* was the first Wagner opera to be performed, in 1883. The title role was sung by the young tenor Oreste Emiliani (1856–?), who was making his debut that same year.

The reception of Wagner in Brazil was particularly noteworthy, as the composer's music, much like in France, was introduced through the upper aristocracy. Emperor Dom Pedro II, known as 'the Magnanimous', was an ardent admirer of Wagner and had even invited him to relocate to Brazil (Fig. 10).

He successfully promoted the composer's music throughout the country. Dom Pedro II was also a member of the Bayreuth Patronat-Verein and did not hesitate to cross the Atlantic to attend the premiere of the *Ring* in 1876 and to meet Wagner in person.

3. Asia

3.1 Japan

Even Asian countries did not remain untouched by the spread of Wagnerism. A particularly noteworthy case is that of Japan, where, at the beginning of the twentieth century, many intellectuals, not only musicians, but also writers and painters, displayed an intense dedication to and feverish enthusiasm for Wagner, despite the fact that the majority of them had never heard a single note of the German master's music. Although Western music had already been incorporated into the court musicians' repertoire as early as 1874, it was not until 1903 that the first Western

⁴⁷ PERETTI 1989, p. 33.

⁴⁸ *ivi*, p. 34

opera was performed in Japan, *Orphée et Euridice* by Gluck, translated into Japanese and staged by Japanese musicians and singers at the University of Tokyo.⁴⁹

In fact, the opera that was originally intended for that occasion was Wagner's *Tannhäuser*, to be accompanied by the Keiō Wagner Society Orchestra, founded in 1901 (and still active today). However, the vocal parts proved too difficult for the singers, and a 'simpler' work was chosen instead. It was not until 1939 that Tokyo witnessed a performance of a Wagner opera: *Lohengrin*, conducted by Manfred Gurlitt (1890–1972), who had emigrated to Japan to escape Nazi persecution.⁵⁰

Japanese Wagnerism even led to the composition of original operatic works inspired by the German composer's style. Among them was *Tokoyami* (常闇, *Eternal Darkness*, 1906), composed by Tōgi Tetteki (1869–1925), Fig. 11, with a libretto by Tsubouchi Shōyō (1859–1935).

The opera's subject matter was drawn from the Japanese myth of Amaterasu Ōmikami, the sun goddess, and followed Wagner's example in its use of mythological material. The music employed the technique of *leitmotive* and incorporated melodies from *gagaku*, the ancient music of the imperial court.

Tsubouchi was also the author of a theoretical treatise infused with Wagnerian ideas, entitled *Shingakugekiron* (新樂劇論, *Treatise on the New Musical Drama*, 1904), in which he proposed the foundation of a new form of musical drama (*Neu-Musikdrama*) aimed at fostering nationalist sentiment during the Russo-Japanese War (1904–1905).⁵¹

Likewise, leading academic figures such as Anesaki Chōfū (1873–1949) went so far as to describe Wagner's music dramas as «a true philosophy and at the same time a true religion, and for that very reason, also true art. Bayreuth is indeed the Jerusalem of this new religion». Equally significant were the words of another Wagnerian theorist of the period, Kondō Itsugorō (1885–1915), who declared that «the people may be redeemed through musical drama».⁵²

3.2 China

Unlike Japan, the reception of Wagner in China occurred later and followed the events of the *May Fourth Movement* in 1919, which was spearheaded by students at Peking University, the moderate bourgeoisie of the capital, and other progressive intellectual circles (Fig. 12).

⁴⁹ GROUT 1995, p. 566.

⁵⁰ *Tannhäuser* would not be staged until 1947. Performed at the Imperial Theatre in Tokyo by the Fujiwara Opera Company, the most prominent Japanese opera troupe at the time, it set an unprecedented attendance record, achieving sold-out status for all 25 performances held over the course of 23 consecutive days. MAUSI 2005, p. 9.

⁵¹ TAKASHI 2007, p. 52.

⁵² *Ivi*, p. 23. It is hardly surprising that the interest in Wagner was so pronounced, and that even at that time there existed both a society and an orchestra bearing his name. German influence on Japanese politics was, in fact, particularly strong during this period, so much so that Japan adopted the Prussian model for its first modern constitution, the Meiji Constitution of 1889.

These groups rejected Confucian tradition and championed Western culture. This form of radicalism was associated with nationalism, which rejected the constraints on Chinese sovereignty imposed by the Treaty of Versailles on the newly established Republic of China.

Initial interest in Wagner in China was largely confined to the realm of music analysis in specialized journals. Later, commentary on Wagner's libretti became a significant part of the first edition of *A Short History of Western Opera Evolution*. *Die Meistersinger von Nürnberg*, translated into Chinese under the title *The Famous Singer*, quickly became regarded as Wagner's most important opera and was the most widely read from a nationalist perspective.⁵³

However, the staging of Wagner's operas, which required highly skilled musicians and singers with specific technical and linguistic expertise, proved extremely challenging. Moreover, the ensuing political events, which led to increasing distrust toward the Western world, further hindered the dissemination of Wagner's work in China.

Interest in Wagner was rekindled only at the end of the 1980s, and the complete Chinese translation of all of Wagner's operas was not published until 1997. The first full performance of a Wagner opera in China, *Der fliegende Holländer*, finally took place in 1999.

Conclusions

Tab. 1 presents a chronological overview of the dates of the first performances of Wagner's operas in various countries across three continents. It is worth noting that the dates of the first performances of Wagner's operas in various countries often followed, sometimes by many years, the initial discussions surrounding the composer and his music.

From the evidence presented above, it may be concluded that the reception of Wagner took markedly diverse forms across different countries. In some cases, such as in the Austro-Hungarian Empire and in Spain, Wagner's reception varied significantly along ethnic or regional lines, resulting in distinct characteristics and outcomes within the same nation-state or imperial context. It can also be inferred that the global spread of Wagnerism was not directly correlated with geographic proximity to its origin in Germany. For instance, countries such as Japan established Wagner societies well before some of their European counterparts. Similarly, in the United States, the Wagnerian movement gained cultural prominence earlier than in several European nations. It should furthermore be emphasized that musical Wagnerism represented only one facet of a broader phenomenon. On a wider cultural level, Wagnerism engaged painters, writers, architects, and, more generally, intellectuals who were captivated by the personality of the *Meister*.

Wagnerism reached its peak in the early years of the twentieth century. Thereafter, Wagner's musical language began to lose its dominant position and was gradually eclipsed by the *avant-garde* movements. At the same time, the rise of alternative

⁵³ HU 2023, p. 1152.

artistic currents contributed to its decline: «Wagner, as man and artist, [...] became simply one of the great composers of the past. Twilight descends upon the gods, yet for a brief moment, it continues to illuminate their works».⁵⁴

⁵⁴ DONALD J. GROUT 1995, p. 499.

Fig. 1: Ernst von Wolzogen (author: anonymous; Publisher: Alfred Schlesinger, Berlin, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 2: Pierre-Auguste Renoir, *Portrait of Richard Wagner*, 1882, Musée d'Orsay, Paris, (Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 3: Edward Burne-Jones, *Laus Veneris*, 1873-75, Laing Art Gallery in Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom (Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 4: Mariano Fortuny, *Wotan hits the rock*, 1894-96, Museo Fortuny, Venezia (Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons)

Fig. 5: Rogelio de Egusquiza, *Kundry*, 1906, Museo del Prado, Madrid (Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 6: Erkki Melartin, ‘the Finnish Wagner’ (Hans Höfer, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 7: Valentin Serov (Hans Höfer, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 8 - Lohengrin catamaran-style boat. The boat was foot-propelled like a bicycle attached to a paddle wheel (website of Swanboats, Boston: <https://swanboats.com/history/> (accessed: 25/07/2025)).

Fig. 9: Auditorium Building Chicago, 1889. Auditorium interior from balcony (JW Taylor, photographer, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 10: Pedro II of Brazil (Mathew Benjamin Brady, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 11: Tōgi Tetteki, 1956 (朝日新聞社, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Fig. 12: May 4 Movement protest at Tiananmen Square, 1919 (Hong Kong Central Library, zh: 香港中央圖書館, exhibition in April 2019 for the celebration of the 100th anniversary of May Fourth Movement, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons).

Tables

Country or Region	Wagner's first work performed
German Conf.	<i>Liebesverbot</i> 1836 Magdeburg, only one performance during Wagner's lifetime); 1842 <i>Rienzi</i> , Dresden
Latvia	1843 <i>Der fliegende Holländer</i> , 1840s Riga
Switzerland	1852 <i>Der fliegende Holländer</i> , 1840s Zurich
Estonia	1853 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Tallinn
Austria	1854 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Graz
Bohemia	1854 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Prague
Belgium	1855 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Antwerp
Holland	1858 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Amsterdam
USA	1859 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , New York
France	1861 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Paris
Hungary	1862 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Budapest
Sweden	1865 <i>Rienzi</i> , Stockholm
Slovakia	1865 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Bratislava
Poland	1865 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Lviv
Russia	1868 <i>Lohengrin</i> , St Petersburg
United Kingdom	1870 <i>Der fliegende Holländer</i> , London
Denmark	1870 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Copenhagen
Italy	1871 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Bologna
Spain	1876 <i>Rienzi</i> , Madrid
Portugal	1883 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Lisbon
Brasil	1883 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Rio de Janeiro
Argentina	1883 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Buenos Aires
Mexico	1890 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Mexico City
Cuba	1883 <i>Lohengrin</i> , L'Avana
Finland	1904 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Helsinki
Romania	1921 <i>Tannhäuser</i> , Klausenburg
Lithuania	1926 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Vilnius
Japan	1939 <i>Lohengrin</i> , Tokyo; unsuccessful attempt to represent <i>Tannhäuser</i> in 1903
China	1999 <i>Der fliegende Holländer</i> , Pechino

Tab. 1: Wagner's works reception in various countries (elaborated from: KUNST 2014, pp. 119-121)

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